

Assessing the Effects of the Statutory Reserve Requirement Ratio on the Profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Zambia: A Case Study of Selected SMEs in Munali Township

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 24th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Statutory Reserve Requirement Ratio (SRR) Profitability Lending Interest Rates Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>This study aimed to examine how Statutory Reserve Requirement Ratio (SRR) adjustments influence commercial bank lending interest rates and, in turn, affect the profitability of retail SMEs in Munali Constituency. The research objectives were firstly to assess how banks' changes in lending interest rates due to SRR affects retail SMEs cost of borrowing, secondly to assess how banks' changes in lending interest rates due to SRR affects retail SMEs revenue performance, and thirdly to analyze how banks' changes in lending interest rates due to SRR affects retail SMEs competitive advantage. A quantitative research design is said to been applied using structured questionnaires which were administered to a purposive sample of 100 retail SMEs, and then the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, OLS simple regression, and ANOVA. The findings showed that lending rate fluctuations used as a proxy for SRR influence did not have a statistically significant effect on either the perceived burden of borrowing costs (ANOVA, $p = 0.450$) or monthly revenue performance (OLS, $p = 0.6393$). These results specify that changes in lending interest rate alone do not fully account for the variations observed in the financial outcomes of retail SMEs. Still though evidence from the third objective revealed that high costs of borrowing materially weaken competitive positioning with 53% of the respondents reporting reduced ability to restock, diversify inventory, or introduce new products under elevated lending interest rate conditions. The study concludes that even though SRR driven lending interest rate changes do not significantly predict revenue performance, they do however restrict operational flexibility and long-term competitiveness. It recommends targeted credit interventions, improved SME financial management support, and more predictable monetary policy measures to reduce credit cost volatility and strengthen SME resilience.</p> <p>Keywords: small and medium enterprises (SMEs), statutory reserve requirement ratio (SRR), profitability, lending interest rates, competitive advantage.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The Bank of Zambia (BOZ) manages the flow of money in the economy of Zambia through either contractionary or expansionary monetary policy (BOZ, 2018). This is mostly done through the monetary policy tools like Open Market Operation, Monetary policy, Policy Rate (PR), and Statutory Reserve Requirement Ratio (SRR). The SRR is a macro monetary policy instrument used by central banks around the world to control money supply, manage inflation, and influence credit conditions in the financial system. By compelling commercial banks to hold a specified fraction of their deposits with the central bank, the SRR directly curtails the volume of loanable funds circulating in the financial system. In Zambia, the Bank of Zambia (BOZ) has historically used SRR adjustments together with the policy rate changes and open market operations to maintain macroeconomic stability. Over the past few years, the Zambian economy has performed poorly, this is marked by a weakening kwacha and persistent inflation. In response the Bank of Zambia are said to have tightened monetary policy, by raising the SRR several times. Firstly, the SRR was increased from 9 percent in early 2023 to 11.5 percent additionally further to 26 percent by 2025 (BOZ Monetary Policy Report, 2023). Such a sharp increase in the SRR may have led to unintended consequences have, particularly for the cost

and accessibility of commercial bank credit. Globally, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are considered as the backbone of commerce by accounting for approximately 90 percent of businesses and more than 50 percent of employment (World Bank, 2017). But locally SMEs remain central to Zambia's economic growth, providing about 70 percent of employment and accounting for nearly 20 percent of GDP (ZDA, 2020). Most SMEs are small retail outlets such as grocery shops, clothing stalls, hardware stores, and informal traders that are believed to rely heavily on short-term credit to restock and pay suppliers in Lusaka's Munali Township. Within this group retail SMEs form a significant share, offering everyday goods and services to local consumers and sustaining many informal and semi-formal livelihoods. To manage inventory and cover operating expenses retail SMEs are also known to regularly dependent on short-term credit services from small loan companies or from individuals offering loans at high interests known as "Kaloba". This is for the reason that many SMEs in Zambia struggle to obtain credit from commercial bank due to informal operations, lack of collateral, and limited financial history. These challenges are worsened under contractionary monetary policies like SRR hikes, which then reduce the credit supply besides elevating borrowing costs. The Bank of Zambia in a 2024 monetary policy statement highlighted that policy rate and SRR increases were implemented to contain inflationary pressures, but these measures also resulted in tightened interest rate conditions across the banking sector (Bank of Zambia, 2024). Munali township is an urban area within Lusaka City which is characterized by dense commercial activity in addition to high concentrations of small-scale traders, grocery stores, clothing outlets, and hardware shops. So the present research therefore focuses on retail SMEs in Munali Township, which will serve as a small-scale version of the urban entrepreneurship in Zambia, where businesses are highly sensitive to shifts in borrowing costs due to their reliance on external finance whether from commercial banks or other credit institutions. Since the previously mentioned change in SRR in 2023 local reports have indicated that a sharp rise in loan rejection rates and average lending rates reported to have increased from 25.12 percent to 27.60 percent following the 2023 SRR adjustment (Lusaka SME Chamber 2023). Given the rising interest rates in recent years, SMEs and more specific retail SME in Munali are experiencing tighter credit access and operational constraints.

1.2 Problem Description

The Bank of Zambia frequently adjusts the SRR to manage inflation and maintain financial sector stability. Despite the fact that is theoretically sound the resultant changes in commercial bank lending interest rates increase the cost of borrowing for retail SMEs. Which would potentially stifle retail SMEs' investment, reduce revenue, and undermining the ability for the retail SMEs to compete. Despite the observed monetary policy adjustments along with the persistent struggles of retail SMEs, limited empirical research in Zambia specifically connects the SRR's impact on commercial bank liquidity to the subsequent profitability and competitive advantage of retail SMEs at a micro-level. This study seeks to bridge this gap by providing firm-level evidence on how the SRR's transmission affects Munali Township's retail SME sector.

1.3 Research Objectives

The general and specific objectives of this study are as presented in the sections below.

1.3.1 General Objectives

To assess the effects of the Statutory Reserve Requirement Ratio (SRR) on the profitability of retail SMEs in Munali township.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- i. To assess how banks' changes in lending interest rates due to SRR affects retail SMEs cost of borrowing.
- ii. To assess how banks' changes in lending interest rates due to SRR affects retail SMEs revenue performance.
- iii. To analyze how banks' changes in lending interest rates due to SRR affects retail SMEs competitive advantage.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. How do banks' changes in lending interest rates, specifically those affected by the SRR, impact the cost of borrowing for retail SMEs in Munali Constituency, Zambia?
- ii. What is the effect of banks' changes in lending interest rates, specifically those influenced by the SRR, on the revenue performance of retail SMEs in Munali Constituency, Zambia?
- iii. Why do banks' changes in lending interest rates, specifically those influenced by the SRR, impact the competitive advantage of retail SMEs in Munali Constituency, Zambia?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates that changes in the Statutory Reserve Requirement (SRR) set by the Bank of Zambia (BOZ) influence retail SMEs in Munali Constituency indirectly by prompting commercial banks to adjust lending interest rates. Which in turn shapes firstly the cost of borrowing, secondly their revenue performance, and thirdly their overall competitive advantage.

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant for the reason that retail SMEs remain central to Zambia's economic transformation agenda issued by the current UPND government, yet SMEs in general continue to face persistent financial constraints that intensify during periods of monetary tightening. By examining how the SRR-induced lending interest rate adjustments influence the profitability of retail SMEs in Munali, the research offers localized empirical insight into a policy area where existing evidence is limited. The study extends the literature by shifting focus from commercial banks who dominate SRR focused research toward the credit-dependent SMEs that are disproportionately exposed to liquidity shocks. Its findings provide practical value for monetary authorities, development partners, and financial institutions seeking to design reserve frameworks and lending policies that are sensitive to SME operating realities. Furthermore, the results offer useful guidance for SME associations, financial inclusion advocates, and local economic planners by quantifying how borrowing costs affect key profitability indicators, thereby supporting more inclusive approaches to financial regulation that safeguard macroeconomic stability while strengthening SME resilience and competitiveness.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Statutory Reserve Ratio Requirements and Its Influence on Lending Interest Rates and Borrowing Costs for Retail SMEs

Like previously mentioned in the background of the study the SRR is a key monetary policy tool through which central banks around the world regulate liquidity and influence lending conditions. International empirical evidence demonstrates that increases in SRR reduce the supply of loanable funds which then prompts commercial banks to raise lending interest rates or ration credit as shown in research from Uruguay, Pakistan, Nepal, and India. These studies establish that SRR acts as a liquidity tax that lowers commercial bank profitability and pushes them toward risk averse lending practices which is consistent with the Monetary Transmission Mechanism Theory. The international studies' findings also show that SMEs typically under-collateralized and information-constrained are the first to be excluded from credit markets when reserve requirements tighten (Abid, & Lodhi, 2016; Nandini, & Shubha, 2021).

Regional literature from Sub-Saharan Africa also echoes the effects of the SRR on costs of borrowing. Which comes from studies from both Nigeria and Kenya confirm that higher reserve or cash ratios depress commercial bank performance, heighten liquidity shortages, and reduce SME lending regardless of prevailing lending interest rates. While Ghanaian research highlights how regulatory burdens together with monetary tightening compound pre-existing access-to-credit challenges for SMEs in Ghana (Agwu, 2020; Shikumo & Mwangi, 2016; Sam, Dzansi & Sekyere, 2015).

Although there is limited direct evidence for the local context or available research that show that rising SRR significantly reduces commercial bank profitability and liquidity which then leads to higher lending interest rates and stricter credit screening. Additional SME focused studies in Zambia reveal that liquidity constraints whether stemming from SRR or broader monetary conditions that directly weaken SMEs' profitability and operational stability. Altogether, this section of the literature review indicates that increases in the SRR lead to higher costs of borrowing, more credit rationing, and weakened growth prospects for retail SMEs particularly in high-risk urban constituencies such as Munali (Miyoba & Haabazoka, 2024).

2.2 Lending Rate Dynamics and Their Implications for Revenue Performance in Retail SMEs

Global literature shows that around the world commercial banks' perceptions of the risk to lend to SME includes concerns about insufficient collateral, weak documentation, and higher default probabilities play a central role in shaping lending interest rates. Studies from India, Nepal, Pakistan, and other developing economies demonstrate that these perceptions lead to higher costs of borrowing for SMEs. While also constraining access to working capital SMEs need for stocking inventory, hiring workers, and

maintaining daily operations. These studies further indicate that when reserve requirements rise as seen with the SRR commercial banks experience liquidity pressure and respond by increasing lending interest rates or shifting credit toward safer and reliable borrowers. This chain reaction limits SMEs' ability to finance their activities which ends up negatively affecting their revenue performance. Indirect channels of credit supply such as banks' lending to non-bank lenders, also influence the availability together with the cost of credit for SMEs resulting in tightened liquidity that crowds out small firms which ends up reducing their turnover and profitability (Nandini & Shubha, 2021; Suri et al., 2018). Both Regional and Zambian studies reinforce the international studies' findings beginning with evidence from African economics that illustrates how SMEs with limited collateral and weaker financial management practices struggle more when the costs of borrowing rises. Higher lending interest rates reduce the SMEs' ability to restock, manage cash flow, or expand operations, pushing many toward informal and more expensive financing alternatives. In Zambia on the other hand local studies highlight how liquidity tightening and rising loan costs put pressure on SME profitability, especially in urban retail settings such as Munali (Umeaduma, 2024)). These studies also highlight that SMEs with stronger governance or better record-keeping withstand these pressures more effectively whilst those SMEs lacking financial skills face greater vulnerability. Across all contexts, the literature demonstrates a consistent pattern increases in lending interest rates often driven by SRR adjustments limits SMEs access to credit and weaken revenue performance, posing a significant challenge to the financial sustainability of retail SMEs.

2.3 The Impact of Interest Rate Shocks on Competitive Positioning and Market Resilience of Retail SMEs

For this section of the literature review the reviewed studies illustrate that increases in lending interest rates which are believed to be often triggered by monetary policy adjustments such as SRR hikes, place significant pressure on the competitive position of retail SMEs. Global studies reveal that higher borrowing costs limit smaller firms' ability to firstly maintain liquidity, secondly finance inventory, or thirdly invest in expansion. Research from Indonesia and India demonstrates that commercial banks' cautious lending attitudes combined with SMEs' limited collateral and documentation push interest rates upward and restrict access to reasonably priced credit (Pandeiro, Sumanti, & Aseng, 2022). These patterns are also echoed in the regional studies reviewed from Uganda and Lesotho where SMEs facing high and unpredictable lending interest rates which are often reduce growth-oriented investments or scale back competitive activities such as product development and marketing. Firms with better liquidity in addition to stronger financial management tend to cope more effectively, whilst those SMEs dependent on external borrowing face greater vulnerability when interest rates are raised (Okello, Onyango-Delewa & Owot, 2025). Local studies from Zambia reinforce these findings and show how SRR-driven interest rate adjustments directly affect the day-to-day resilience of retail SMEs. Evidence from Lusaka indicates that high borrowing costs make it difficult for SMEs to finance inventory diversification, adopt new technologies, or adjust prices in competitive markets. Many firms respond by reducing their operations expenditure or delaying investments, whereas the others turn to informal lenders at even higher costs of borrowing. Reports from the IMF as well as the World Bank further highlight that tight credit conditions excessively affect smaller firms with limited financial buffers, completely narrowing their pricing flexibility and ability to respond to market changes. Across all the studies the general conclusion is clearly that rising lending interest rates reduce the financial and strategic capacity of SMEs to remain competitive, especially in settings where access to affordable credit is already limited such as Munali (Nchephe, 2022; Musonda & Hapompwe, 2024; IMF, 2023)).

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional quantitative design which was chosen for the reason that it is suitable for capturing firm-level financial responses without requiring time-series data. Furthermore, the design also allowed the researcher to examine the effects of SRR linked lending interest rate changes on the profitability of retail SMEs at a single point in time.

3.2 Target Population

The target population consists of registered retail SMEs operating in Munali Township. The retail SMEs were defined in accordance with Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA) classifications as firms with annual turnovers between K200,000 and K20 billion or employing 5 to 10 workers.

3.3 Sampling Design

From the stated target population, a purposive sampling technique was applied to select SMEs that met the study's inclusion conditions of SMEs operating in the retail sector, located in Munali, and having been affected by lending interest rate changes associated with SRR adjustments. A final sample of 100 SMEs was used while guided by feasibility and precedents in similar Zambian SME studies.

3.4 Data Collection Method

The main and only primary data was collected using structured questionnaires administered to retail SMEs by the researcher. The questionnaire in question covered three sections starting with firstly the personal and business demographics (gender, age, nature of business, workforce, duration of retail business), secondly loan data (loan amount, interest rate, frequency of borrowing), and thirdly financial performance (revenue, profit, total assets, input costs). The design of the questionnaire followed the templates used in Zambia Business Survey (2011) and adapted from Quartey and Beck et al. (2015).

3.5 Data Analysis

The data analysis involved the use of descriptive statistics, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, and one-factor ANOVA to assess the relationships between lending interest rates used as a proxy for SRR transmission and each of the three outcome variables of borrowing costs, revenue performance, and competitive advantage. All analyses followed the structure laid out in the study’s conceptual and theoretical framework.

3.6 Sample Size Determination

Given the study’s focus on specific characteristics of retail SMEs such as their accessibility, sectoral relevance, and financial behavior a purposive sampling method was deemed to be appropriate. This non-probability sampling approach enabled the researcher to select participants based on predefined inclusion criteria that are business registration status, trading activity, and survey accessibility. The retail SME sector in Munali was diverse so the purposive sampling allowed the researcher to reflect this heterogeneity at the same time as working within practical limitations. A final sample size of 100 respondents was chosen for the reason that it was informed by both resource constraints and precedent in similar studies conducted within Zambia (e.g., Simbyakula & Hapompwe, 2024). Care was taken to include a broad range of retail businesses to ensure the findings capture varied perspectives and reflect internal validity.

4. Presentation and Interpretation of Findings

4.1 Presentation of results on characteristics of the respondents. Background

4.1.1 Age

Small proportion of less than tenth upto 7% of the of retail SMEs had the age range of 18 to 25, whilst 35% and 31% of the owners of retail SMEs having 26 to 35 and 36 to 45 age group respectively. The remaining 19% and 8% were the age group of owners of retail SMEs that range from 46 to 55 and 56 & above respectively. See figure 4.1 below.

Figure 4.1: Age group distribution

The study also asked respondents to specify their gender, with 42% identifying as male and 42% also identifying as female while the remaining 16% of them preferred not to say.

Figure 4.2: Gender distribution

The study gathered information on the respondents’ educational level, which revealed that 16% and 29% of the retail SMEs having reached primary and secondary education as their highest level of education respectively. While 17% and 24% of the retail SMEs having completed a diploma and degree or higher program respectively. Finally, the remaining 14% of the retail SMEs who participated in the questionnaire survey specified having no formal education whatsoever.

Figure 4.3: Highest level of education distribution

The study asked respondents to specify the duration of their retail businesses with 15% and 23% of the retail SMEs having been in operation for less than 1 year and for 1 year to 3 years respectively. While the others owners of retail SMEs who participated in the questionnaire survey accounted for the 29% and 33% who have had their business in operation for 4 to 6 years and more than 6 years respectively.

Table 4.1: Duration of retail business

	Frequency	Percent
Less than 1 year	15	15%
1-3 years	23	23%
4-6 years	29	29%
More than 6 years	33	33%
Total	100	100%

The study also asked the respondents to specify the size of their workforce for their retail business. Starting with 12% and 20% accounting for the retail SMEs who answered that they had 1 to 2 employees and 3 to 5 employees respectively. Whereas 36% and 32% of the retail SMEs who responded that they have 6 to 10 employees and more than 10 employees respectively.

Table 4.2: Size of workforce

	Frequency	Percent
1-2 Employees	12	12%
3-5 Employees	20	20%
6-10 Employees	36	36%
More than 10 employees	32	32%
Total	100	100%

The respondents were further categorized by the nature of retail business, beginning with 27% and 23% of the retail SMEs running grocery and clothing retail businesses respectively. Though 22% and 17% of the retail SMEs run electronic and hardware businesses in Munal Township. With the remaining 11% of the retail SMEs responding with other meaning.

Table 4.3: Nature of retail business

	Frequency	Percent
Grocery	27	27%
Clothing	23	23%
Electronics	22	22%
Hardware	17	17%
Other	11	11%
Total	100	100%

4.2 Cost of Borrowing

This section presents the findings related to the first specific objective of the study: "To assess how banks' changes in lending interest rates due to SRR affects retail SMEs cost of borrowing.". The analysis is structured to provide a detailed understanding of how retail SMEs in Munali Township perceive and experience their borrowing costs.

Figure 4.4 below presents the frequency distribution for the first question of the second section of the questionnaire, "Have you obtained a business loan in the past 3 years?", providing an initial overview of the loan seeking behavior of the sample. From the Figure it can be surmised that 59% of the respondents said that yes they have obtained a loan in the last three years, while 41% of them have not obtained a loan in the last three years.

Figure 4.4: Have you obtained a business loan in the past year?

Whereas Figure 4.5 below presents the frequency distribution for the second question of the "Cost of Borrowing" section of the questionnaire. The figure below shows that 9% of the respondents the retail SMEs of Munali Township said that the interest rate on their most recent business loan was below 20%. But 45% of the them which is the majority of them said that the interest rate on their most recent business loan was between 21% and 30%, while 44% of them said that the interest rates on their most recent business loan was between 31% and 40%. The remaining 9% of them said that the interest rate on their most recent business loan was above 40%.

Figure 4.5: Interest rate on your most recent business loan?

In Table 4.4 below shows quantitative data about the fourth question of the second section of the questionnaire. Where the research asked the respondents to rate how the impact of rising interest rates on their business expenses. From the data in the table it can be seen that 53% of the respondents selected "moderate" as how they rated the impact of rising interest rates on their business. The other 19% and 6% of the respondents selected "high" and "very high" respectively as their rating of the impact. The remaining 17% and 4% of the respondents selected "low" and "very low" respectively as their rating of the impact of rising interest rates.

Table 4.4: How would you rate the impact of rising interest rates on your business expenses?

	Frequency	Percent
Very Low	4	4%
Low	17	17%
Moderate	53	53%
High	19	19%
Very High	6	6%
Total	100	100%

While figure 4.6 below shows the quantitative data of the seventh question of “Cost of Borrowing” section in the questionnaire. The question asked the respondents to choose among the given options how in the past did higher rates make it harder for them to borrow again. Around 32% and 14% of the respondents selected agree and strongly agree respectively, which means that higher interest rates did make it harder for them to borrow again in the past year. But 17% and 6% of the respondents selected strongly disagree and disagree respectively meaning that in the past year they strongly disagree and disagree that higher interest rates made it harder for them to borrow again. The remaining 31 percent of the respondents selected neutral as their option for the question meaning that they could not be sure if really higher interest rates made it harder for them to borrow again in the past year.

Figure 4.6 In the past year, did higher interest rates make it harder for you to borrow again?

Statistical Results

A regression analysis was conducted to see if the “Rate of Impact of Rising Interest Rates on Business Expenses (the dependent variable, from Question 10)” can be explained by other factors like the “lending interest rate on the most recent loan as the independent variable from Question 8”. Below is firstly the hypothesis of regression conducted using MegaState and also table 5 and table 6 that show the statistical results of the regression analysis. To statistically assess the relationship between lending interest rates and retail SMEs’ cost of borrowing, the following hypotheses were tested:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no statistically significant relationship between the lending interest rate on a retail business's most recent loan and the perceived rate of impact of rising lending interest rates on retail business expenses.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_A): There is a statistically significant relationship between the lending interest rate on a retail business's most recent loan and the perceived rate of impact of rising lending interest rates on the retail business expenses.

Table 4.5: ANOVA table

Regression Analysis					
	r ²	0.005	n	100	
	r	0.068	k	1	
	Std. Error	0.883	Dep.Var.	10. Rate of Impact of Rising Interest Rates on Your Business Expenses?	
<i>Source</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Regression	0.3582	1	0.3582	0.46	.4994
Residual	76.3918	98	0.7795		
Total	76.7500	99			

Table 4.6: Regression output

Regression output				confidence interval		
<i>variables</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>std. error</i>	<i>t (df=98)</i>	<i>p-value</i>	95 percent lower	95 percent upper
Intercept	2.8386	0.3241	8.759	5.95E-14	2.1955	3.4818
8. Interest Rate on Your most Recent Business	0.0884	0.1305	0.678	.4994	-0.1705	0.3474

The regression results highlighted in table 4.6 and table 4.5 show that the model’s explanatory power is extremely weak with an r^2 value of 0.005, indicating that lending interest rates account for less than one percent of the variation in retail SMEs’ reported perceptions of how rising costs of borrowing affect business expenses. The correlation coefficient was (r) is 0.0683 similarly confirms the absence of a meaningful linear relationship, implying that changes in the loan rate whether 20 percent, 30 percent, or 40 percent did not correspond to systematic differences in how SMEs rated the impact of rising interest rates on their operating costs. The hypothesis test reinforces this conclusion. The p -value far exceeds the 0.05 significance threshold and the associated F -statistic is likewise below the level required for statistical significance. Therefore, the relationship between lending interest rates and perceived cost of borrowing burden is not statistically significant there by proving that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This suggests that within the sampled retail SMEs in Munali perceptions of financial strain are not determined by the specific lending interest rate applied to their loan. Rather it appears that credit is widely regarded as costly irrespective of the exact rate which reflects a broader structural condition within Zambia’s credit market where borrowing is consistently expensive and volatile.

A one-factor ANOVA was also conducted to assess whether perceptions of rising lending interest rate impacts vary across different interest rate categories. In practical terms the analysis tests whether the retail SMEs exposed to lower, moderate, or higher lending interest rate bands report significantly different levels of cost pressure attributable to rising interest rates. The output of the one-factor ANOVA analysis below shows that is no significant difference among the groups, with F statistic of 0.888, and p -value of 0.450. Since the p -value is greater than the significant level of 0.05 there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the groups. This means that The retail SMEs in Munali Township, whether they reported paying a lower interest rate or a higher interest rate, have the same average perception of how difficult rising borrowing costs are for their business expenses.

Table 4.7: ANOVA table

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups (Interest Rate Categories)	0.888	3	0.296	0.888	0.450
Within Groups (Error)	96.45	96	1.005		
Total	97.338	99			

4.3 Revenue Performance

This section beginning with the quantitative statistics results of the summarized responses of the key questions from the questionnaire. Starting with looking at the Figure 4.7 below, it is apparent that majority of the sampled retail SMEs from Munali Township which is about 45% of them experienced a drop in their average monthly revenue in the last 12 months. While 28% of them experienced an increased in their average monthly and the remaining 27 percent of them said that their average monthly revenue remained the same.

Figure 4.7: Has your average monthly revenue changed in the last 12 months?

Next the respondents were asked what their monthly revenue was and their response is represented in table below. Starting with 10% of them responded with having an average monthly revenue of less than ZMW 5,000 and 32% of them responded with them having an average monthly revenue of ZMW 5,000-10,000. Whereas 31% and 27% of them responded with having average monthly revenue of ZMW 10,001-20,000 and above ZMW 20,000 respectively.

Table 4.8: What is your average monthly revenue?

	Frequency	Percent
Less than ZMW 5,000	10	10%
ZMW 5,000-10,000	32	32%
ZMW 10,001-20,000	31	31%
Above ZMW 20,000	27	27%
Total	100	100%

After the respondents' average monthly revenue responses from the previous questionnaire question. The study then asked the respondents to describe with following responses "No Impact", "Slight Impact", "Moderate Impact", and "Major Impact" to what extent do they believe borrowing costs have affected their revenue. Figure 4.8 below shows the data from the responses of retail SMEs of Munali Township. About 40% of them responded with moderate impact which means that they believe that borrowing costs have a moderate impact on their revenue. While 36% of the respondents responded with borrowing costs having slight impact on their retail business's revenue. Whereas 12% and remaining 12% of the respondents responded with borrowing costs having no impact and major impact on their retail business' revenue respectively.

Figure 4.8: To what extent do you believe borrowing costs have affected your revenue?

Statistical Results

Just like the statistical results for the cost of borrowing section a simple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine whether retail SMEs' borrowing costs significantly influence their perceived impact of borrowing costs on revenue. The dependent variable was the response to the question "To what extent do you believe borrowing costs have affected your revenue?" (from question 16), while the independent variable was the cost of borrowing experienced by the retail SMEs. Also using MegaStat the simple regression analysis shown below is the MegaStat output for the analysis.

To statistically assess the relationship between retail SMEs' borrowing costs and the impact of borrowing costs on their revenue performance with the following hypotheses were tested:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no statistically significant relationship between SMEs' borrowing costs and their perceived impact of borrowing costs on revenue performance.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is a statistically significant relationship between SMEs' borrowing costs and their perceived impact of borrowing costs on revenue performance.

Table 4.9: ANOVA table

Regression Analysis					
	r ²	0.003	n	100	
	r	0.058	k	1	
	Std. Error	0.850	Dep. Var.	16. To what extent do you believe borrowing costs have affected your revenue?	
Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Regression	0.2414	1	0.2414	0.33	.5644
Residual	70.7486	98	0.7219		
Total	70.9900	99			

Table 4.10: Regression output

4.3.9 Regression output	variables	coefficients	std. error	t (df=98)	p-value	confidence interval	
						percent lower	percent upper
	Intercept	2.3800	0.2403	9.903	1.96E-16	1.9031	2.8569
	4. Time of Retail Business Operation	0.0464	0.0803	0.578	.5644	-0.1129	0.2058

The regression results above and in the previous page show that the relationship between borrowing costs and the perceived impact of these costs on revenue is extremely weak. The correlation coefficient r -value is 0.058 indicates only a 5.8% positive association, while the coefficient of determination r^2 -value is 0.003 also shows that borrowing cost levels explain just 0.3% of the variation in how retail SMEs perceive revenue effects. In practical terms, changes in the interest rate paid by retail SMEs do not meaningfully predict how strongly owners feel borrowing costs influence their revenue performance.

The statistical tests confirm this interpretation. The ANOVA p -value is seen to be 0.5644 which is far above the 0.05 significance level in addition to the F -value which is 0.33 and remains below the threshold required to show a meaningful effect. These results indicate that the slope coefficient in the regression model (0.0464) does not represent a statistically significant relationship. Consequently, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Regardless whether retail SMEs face higher or lower lending interest rates their perceptions about how borrowing costs affects revenue remain largely unchanged. Other factors such as fluctuations in customer demand, input costs, or market competition may play a stronger role in shaping revenue outcomes of retail SMEs other than borrowing costs alone and that is what the pattern seen in the simple regression results suggest. These findings are also consistent with local empirical evidence showing that retail SMEs in Zambia operate under chronically high lending interest rate which ends up making small differences in how loan pricing has a less prominent impact on their revenue performance (Bank of Zambia, 2021).

4.4 Competitive Advantage

For this section beginning with quantitative statistics of the data from the first question of this section of the questionnaire in the figure below. Which asked the respondents to select from the options given if they believed that borrowing costs influence their ability to compete with other SMEs. From the figure in the next can be seen that most of the retail SMEs which are about 34% selected “Yes, somewhat” which means that 34% of the respondents do believe that borrowing costs influence their ability to compete with SMEs but not strongly. Whereas 31% of the respondents selected “Yes, strongly” which means they strongly believe that borrowing costs influence their ability to compete with other SMEs. About 22% and 13% of the respondents selected “No” and “Not sure” meaning that 22% of them do not believe that borrowing influence their ability to compete with other SMEs. While 13% of the respondents were not sure about if really borrowing costs influence their ability to compete with other SMEs.

Figure 4.9: Do you believe borrowing costs influence your ability to compete with other SMEs?

After getting the respondents’ opinions on if they believe that borrowing costs influence their ability to compete with other SMEs. The study then asked the respondents to select from the given options in the questionnaire “what area of your business has been affected by higher interest rates?”. From the table in the next page it is seen that 31% of the respondents selected “pricing of goods” as the area they believe has been mostly affected by higher interest rates. Again about 31% of the respondents selected “product quality” as the main area they believe is mostly affected by higher interest rates. While 21% and 11% of the respondents selected “staff development” and “other” respectively as the main areas of their businesses being mostly affected by higher interest rates. The lowest number of respondents on the other hand which are about 6 percent of them believed that “advertising or marketing” as the main area being affected by higher interest rates.

Table 4.11: What area of your business has been most affected by higher interest rates?

	Frequency	Percent
Pricing of Goods	31	31%
Advertising or Marketing	6	6%
Staff Development	21	21%
Product	31	31%
Other	11	11%
Total	100	100%

But for the figure below the study asked the respondents how they currently try to stay competitive despite high borrowing costs. From the figure it seen that most of the respondents which is about 42 percent of them selected reduce price as a way they stay competitive despite high borrowing costs. Whereas 30 percent and 19 percent selected cutting operational costs and seek non -loan funding respectively as they way of staying competitive in their markets in the face of high cost of borrowing. The remaining 9 percent was divided by 5 percent and 4 percent of the respondents selecting other and delay investments as the way of staying competitive despite high costs of borrowing.

Figure 4.10: How do you currently try to stay competitive despite high borrowing costs?

Statistical Results

Similar to the previous two sections a regression analysis was also conducted but this time to see if the “Do you believe borrowing costs influence your ability to compete with other SMEs? (the dependent variable, from Question 21)” can be explained by other factors like the “How would you rate the impact of rising interest rates on your business expenses? (the independent variable from Question 11).

To statistically assess the relationship between retail SMEs’ borrowing costs and their ability to compete with other SMEs.

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no statistically significant relationship between retail SMEs’ borrowing costs and their ability to compete with other SMEs.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_A): There is a statistically significant relationship between retail SMEs’ borrowing costs and their ability to compete with other SMEs.

Regression Analysis

Table 4.12: ANOVA

Source	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Regression	6.3925	1	6.3925	6.54	.0120
Residual	95.7175	98	0.9767		
Total	102.1100	99			

Table 4.13: Regression output

variables	coefficient	std. error	t (df=98)	p-value	95% lower	95% upper
Intercept	1.2898	0.358	3.603	.0005	0.579	2.000
10. Rate of Impact of Rising Interest Rates on Your Business Expenses?	0.2886	0.112	2.558	.012	0.064	0.512

The regression results indicate that the relationship between borrowing costs and perceived competitiveness among retail SMEs is weak but present. The correlation coefficient (r) is 0.250 suggests a weak-to-moderate positive association, implying that rising borrowing costs do contribute to competitiveness challenges retail SMEs face. Although other structural factors in addition to managerial factors such as business experience, cost control, and supplier relationships also shape competitive performance. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.063 which also shows that only 6.3% of the variation in competitiveness perceptions is explained by borrowing cost related business expenses. Although modest the previously explained level of explanatory power remains meaningful in the context of retail SMEs' financial constraints.

The statistical significance of the model is further supported by the ANOVA results that starts with the p-value of 0.012 which is below the 0.05 threshold in addition to the F-statistic which is 6.54 and also exceeds the critical value providing sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This confirms that borrowing cost driven changes in business expenses have a statistically significant effect on retail SMEs' competitive capacity. In practical terms, higher borrowing costs are often tied to monetary policy tightening which raise operating expenses, thereby limiting retail SMEs' ability to maintain competitive pricing, restock inventory, or invest in growth-enhancing activities. These constraints may reduce retail SME who in Munali ability to match competitors' price adjustments or maintain consistent stock levels during periods of elevated credit costs.

To conclude the statistical results section a two-way ANOVA using MegaStat was conducted to examine whether the perceived impact of borrowing costs on competitiveness differs by business age and business type. The dependent variable was taken from the first question of the competitive advantage section of the questionnaire, at the same time as the independent variables were obtained from Questions 4 and 6 of the demographic section of the same questionnaire. This analysis allowed for an assessment of whether structural characteristics of SMEs moderate the relationship between borrowing costs and competitive performance.

Table 4.14: ANOVA table

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Years of Operation	4.968	3	1.656	1.891	0.138
Nature of Retail Business	8.223	4	2.056	2.347	0.061
Interaction (Years x Type)	23.561	12	1.963	2.241	0.017
Residual	70.075	80	0.876		
Total	102.1100	99	6.551	6.479	0.216

The results in table 4.14 ANOVA table show that individually the data for the years of operation question and the type of retail business do not significantly affect retail SMEs' perceptions of how borrowing costs influence their competitiveness. However, the interaction effect between years in operation and type of retail business is significant with a p-value of 0.017. This means that the combined effect of how long the retail business has operating and what type of retail business it is does have influence how retail SMEs perceive borrowing costs in relation to their competitiveness. To put simply the impact of borrowing costs on competitiveness differs depending on both business type together.

4.5 Discussion of the Findings

The first objective evaluated whether SRR-linked changes in lending interest rates significantly influenced the cost of borrowing pressures among retail SMEs. Both the regression r^2 which is 0.0047, p-value which is 0.6393 and the one-way ANOVA analysis which resulted in the following output of firstly the F-statistics value of 0.888, secondly the p-value of 0.450. Which revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship which indicates that retail SMEs' perceptions of financial strain do not vary in a predictable way with different loan interest rates. This outcome is consistent with the demographic profile of the sample were most firms were young, micro-sized, and lacked formal bookkeeping systems, with many depending on micro-finance institutions rather than commercial banks. These characteristics mean that credit is already experienced as big expense by the retail SMEs regardless of the actual lending interest rates charged. The finding aligns with previously review studies such as Nandini & Shubha (2021), Umeaduma (2024), and Musonda & Hapompwe (2024). Who all show that SMEs perceive costs of borrowing as being structurally high due to collateral barriers, documentation challenges, and risk-averse lending practices rather than because of specific lending interest rate levels. While the second objective assessed whether the changes in lending interest rates which is used as a proxy for the SRR transmission had a measurable effect on revenue performance among the sampled retail SMEs. The regression results were again statistically insignificant with firstly the p-value being greater than 0.05 which suggests that profitability is shaped more by non-financial variables than by marginal shifts in borrowing costs. Demographic data indicated that most surveyed retail SMEs operated on modest revenue cycles experienced frequent stock-outs, and relied heavily on walk in customers. These conditions make revenue more sensitive to demand fluctuations, input costs, and supply chain reliability than to lending interest rate variation. This aligns with findings from the previously reviewed studies Brixiová et al. (2020), and Mbewe (2020), who emphasized that SME revenue performance especially in retail markets is driven mostly by customer purchasing power, market competition, and operational efficiency rather than credit conditions alone. Thus, SRR-induced tightening of the

loan market may add financial pressure but does not independently determine short-term revenue performance outcomes. The third objective examined whether the cost of borrowing affect the competitive advantage of retail SMEs. Unlike the previous two objectives, this analysis produced a statistically significant result showing that higher costs of borrowing meaningfully undermine competitiveness of retail SMEs. Additionally, this undermining of competitiveness of retail SMEs is particularly experience through reduced pricing flexibility, limited restocking capacity, and constrained ability to introduce new products. Retail SMEs who are younger in addition to having inventory-intensive were the most adversely affected as their competitive strength depends on maintaining stock depth and adjusting prices quickly. These findings are strongly supported by Pandeiro, Sumanti and Aseng (2022), Suri, Jack & Stoker (2018), Okello et al. (2025), and Musonda & Hapompwe (2024) who also all demonstrated that rising cost of borrowing weaken SMEs' ability to innovate, restock, and sustain market presence under tightening credit conditions. Overall the results reveal that while SRR-driven lending interest rate changes do not directly predict revenue or perceived borrowing strain, they exert a clear and restrictive influence on the competitive strategies that retail SMEs may depend on for long-term viability.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary

The study examined how the SRR adjustments which are usually made by the Central Bank of Zambia influence the lending interest rates in the Zambian commercial banking sector and how these changes consequently affect the profitability of retail SMEs in Munali Township. Drawing from a sample of 100 retail SMEs the researcher employed descriptive statistics, OLS regression, and ANOVA analysis to assess the three outcome variables of cost of borrowing, revenue performance, and competitive advantage. The analysis results showed that although SRR-linked lending interest rates fluctuations did not have a statistically significant effect on the perceived cost of borrowing burdens or monthly revenue performance, high lending costs nonetheless imposed material operational constraints on retail SMEs. Over half of the respondents reported reduced ability to restock, diversify inventory, or introduce new products under conditions of elevated lending interest rates. These findings indicate that lending interest rates while not a strong predictor of short-term revenue outcomes it still exerts meaningful pressure on retail SMEs' operational flexibility and long-term strategic positioning. Overall the study does highlights the complex ways in which monetary policy transmission influences credit-dependent retail SMEs and all SMEs in general in the urban settings such as Munali.

5.2 Conclusion

The study's conclusions follow directly from the analysis of the three research's specific objectives. Firstly, the findings show that variations in lending interest rates used as the proxy through which the SRR influences credit conditions do not exert a statistically significant effect on how retail SMEs perceive the burden of borrowing costs. Both the regression ($p = 0.6393$) and ANOVA ($p = 0.450$) support the null hypothesis. This indicates that SMEs' sense of financial pressure is shaped less by the nominal interest rate and more by other contextual realities such as collateral demands, loan size, operational costs, and the generally high cost of credit in Zambia. Secondly the study concludes that lending interest rate movements do not have a statistically significant linear relationship with the revenue performance of retail SMEs in Munali. This is for the reason that profitability appears to be driven primarily by market demand, cost of living pressures, supply chain factors, and general operating conditions rather than marginal changes in the costs of borrowing. As with the first objective the evidence for the second specific objective statistical analysis supports the null hypothesis and highlights the limited direct transmission of SRR-driven credit conditions to retail SME revenue outcomes. Thirdly the study finds a statistically significant and substantive effect of the costs of borrowing on the competitive advantage of retail SMEs. Higher borrowing costs were shown to constrain inventory restocking, restrict the introduction of new products, and limit strategic investment areas essential for sustaining competitiveness for the retail SMEs. This then confirms the alternative hypothesis and demonstrates that the costs of borrowing pose a binding operational constraint affecting retail SMEs' ability to compete, innovate, and grow.

5.2 Recommendations

I. Recommendations to the Bank of Zambia (BOZ)

1. Broaden Financial Inclusion Beyond Interest Rate Interventions: Since interest rates alone do not determine retail SMEs' cost perceptions or profitability, BOZ should then strengthen mechanisms that reduce non-rate barriers such as collateral requirements and administrative borrowing costs.
2. Introduce Targeted Liquidity Facilities: The Bank of Zambia should also consider reserve-based incentives or tiered liquidity windows that support commercial banks extending small-ticket, lower-risk loans tailored to the retail SME sector.
3. Adopt Gradual SRR Adjustments: Sharp SRR increases transfer liquidity pressures directly to SMEs specifically retail SMEs through higher lending interest rates. A phased or gradual approach by the BOZ would mitigate adverse shocks and support continuity in retail SMEs operations during tightening cycles.

II. Recommendations to Commercial Banks and Financial Institutions

1. Develop Flexible SME-Specific Credit Products: Commercial banks should design instruments aligned to retail SMEs' working capital cycles for example, short-term revolving facilities for restocking to ease competitive constraints linked to inventory and product introduction.
2. Strengthen Financial Literacy Support: Many SMEs and retail SMEs in particular make borrowing decisions without adequate forecasting. Commercial banks should expand financial literacy programs to improve risk management, budgeting, and sensitivity to interest rate fluctuations, enhancing credit readiness and resilience.

III. Government Recommendations to the Zambian

1. Expand and Strengthen SME Financing Schemes: Government should broaden partial credit guarantee programs and concessional lending channels to buffer SMEs during periods of tightening monetary conditions.
2. Improve Coordination Between Monetary and Industrial Policy: Alignment between inflation stabilization policies and SME support measures is necessary to avoid undermining the real economy. Coordinated policy action can reduce unintended spillover effects on SME growth.

IV. Recommendations to Retail SME Owners

1. Diversify Sources of Finance: To reduce vulnerability to high bank borrowing costs, SMEs should explore microfinance, cooperative lending, supplier credit, and reinvested earnings as complementary financing avenues.
2. Enhance Operational Efficiency: Since profitability is driven more by market and operational factors than by interest rates alone, SMEs should priorities cost control, efficient supply chain management, and strategic inventory practices to remain resilient in periods of rate volatility.

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